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How Different Styles of Conflict Management Determine Creativity? Exploring Petrochemical Companies in Oman

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Abstract

Can conflict be turned into creativity if managed in a certain style? This study aims to explore the impact of conflict management styles (Collaboration, Avoidance, and Accommodation) on the creativity in the Petrochemical companies in Oman. Using a questionnaire, data have been collected, applying simple random method, from employees working in two petrochemical organizations. A final 147 questionnaires were valid for statistical analysis. Multiple regression analysis was utilized to investigate the impact of the styles of conflict management on creativity. The results show that only two styles of conflict management, namely (Collaboration and Accommodation) have an effect on creativity, while Avoidance style found to have no significant effect. The implications of this study are discussed.

Keywords: Styles of Conflict Management, Creativity, Collaboration, Avoidance, Accommodation, Petrochemical Companies, Oman

I. INTRODUCTION

The conflict has been found since the existence of humanity on earth; the first human conflict was between Cain and Abel, Adam's sons. It is considered an inevitable part of dynamic growth or decline (Bercovitch, 1983). In addition, several types or levels of conflict exist, such as conflict that occurs within an individual (intra-personal), conflict between individuals (inter-personal), conflict within a group (intra-group), conflict between groups (inter-group), and conflict within organizations (intra-organizational) (Bercovitch, 1983; Madalina, 2016). Previous research noted that conflict comprises several benefits such as motivating individuals, satisfying certain psychological needs, providing creative and innovative ideas, adding variety to one's organizational life,

and facilitating an understanding of the problems (Omisore and Abiodun, 2014). Thus, the conflict within an organization is not always negative.

On the other hand, new ideas are essential to the survival and success of an organization, and their lacking put the organization at risk of losing excellence and leadership in the market. Heffernan (2015) mentioned that to get true innovation and good ideas, human conflict, interaction, debate, and argument are needed. Chen et al. (2012) also asserted that if the conflict is managed properly, it can increase creative problem-solving, improve interpersonal relationship satisfaction, and lead to better profitability, creativity, and efficiency. Therefore, conflict can be seen as vital and useful to organizations where it can increase productivity and innovativeness, stimulate creative solutions if the right style of conflict management is utilized (Gonçalves et al., 2016; Owens and Valesky, 2007). However, it still remains unclear which style of conflict management is more constructive from the perspective of creativity. Hence, this study came to clarify the effect of the different styles of conflict management on creativity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conflict Management Styles

Conflict management implicates planning effective strategies to reduce the abnormality of conflict and to boost the constructive functionality of conflict in order to enhance organizational effectiveness (Rahim, 2002). It also involves taking rapid and effective measures defined to avoid nonproductive conflict when possible (Shahhosseinia and Taghizadeh, 2016; Madalina, 2016). Conflicts have a significant effect on the outcomes of an organization, and to attain the optimal outcome, conflicts must be appropriately resolved (Wang et al., 2016). In addition, conflict management indicates not only conflict resolution but conflict stimulation, too. There is a desired level of conflict that maximizes organizational performance (Verma, 1998). Another point of view is that managers are eager to know how to stimulate a conflict at optimal levels to boost risk-taking, creativity and long-term performance (Rahim, 2001).

Conflict management styles can be defined as the behaviors people enact during conflicts. In the Dual-Concern Model (Pruitt and Carnevale, 1993; Pruitt and Rubin, 1986; Rahim, 1983) conflict management styles can be situated along two dimensions, namely 1) concern for the own outcomes (won interests) and 2) concern for others' outcomes (relational interests) that lead to four basic styles of conflict: accommodation, avoidance, collaboration and Forcing.

In *accommodation* style, low care for one party's own goal combined with high attention to the benefits of or the relationship with the other party. So, here the accommodating party agrees with the wishes, needs, and ideas of the other party. Therefore, the more constructive opinion may not be utilized due to this style. In addition, inappropriate use of this style may lead to loss of relation that they wish to maintain (Huan & Yazdanifard, 2012). Another term has been used for accommodation in the literature is yielding and Obliging (Oetzel et al., 2001)

In *avoidance* style, conflict issue receives little attention because the problem is trivial or minor and avoiding parry wish to stay away of any confrontation with the other party (Van Erp et al., 2011). This style is real in collectivistic cultures, mainly in Asian societies (Oetzel et al., 2001). People in this style always stay away from conflict, they pretend that everything is okay. People who favor the avoidance style tend to ignore conflict (Rahim, Antonioni, and Psenicka, 2001). They usually use this style to maintain a harmonious situation (Huang, 1999). The benefit of avoidance style is that it can maintain the relationship between employees and managers in the organization, while the weakness of this style that it does not resolve the conflict. In fact, avoiding the problem does not make it go away, but make it worse (Montoya-Weiss, Massey and Song, 2001). In addition, it is inappropriate style when the immediate act is needed or when the two parties can not postpone (Rahim, 2002). In *collaboration* style, high attention to one's own goals combined at the same time with high attention to the interests of the other party. So, here one party agree with the wishes and ideas of another party. It is a win-win

style that search for creative and optimal solutions that meet both parties' interests. Another term has been used for accommodation in the literature is cooperation, problem-solving, or integrating (Leung et al., 1990). In this style, people clear away the conflict with a solution acceptable to all parties to make all parties satisfied with the final resolution (Montoya-Weiss et al., 2001). People follow this style attend and communicate the conflict openly and neutrality with the other parties (Flanagan & Runde, 2008).

In *forcing* style, one party imposes a solution on the other party with care for one's own goal combined with little attention to the interests of or the relationship with the other party. Different terms have been used for forcing in the literature such as contending, dominating, or adversarial style (Baillien et al., 2014). Persons who use this behavior to solve the conflict may force other persons in order to achieve their objectives. They use threats, intimidate and authorities styles to force the parties to agree with it (Lussier, 2010). Therefore, this style is considered a negative conflict management style that may decrease group performance, and it creates anger and aggression toward its users (Huan & Yazdanifard, 2012). However, one advantage of the forcing style is enhancing the organizational decisions if the force is correct.

However, in the current study, only three styles of conflict management from the Dual-Concern Model will be addressed, namely accommodation, avoidance, and collaboration. Forcing style was excluded from this study due to the collective culture of Oman. Several researchers noted that people in collective culture tend to prefer harmony-enhancing styles of conflict management (Barnlund, 1989; Leung et al., 1990). In addition, forcing style tend to extremely harm the relationship and lead to bullying in the organizations (Baillien et al., 2014).

Creativity

Creativity is defined as new and useful ideas, rules and procedures that restrict improvisation and experimentation (Sarooghi et al., 2015). It also refers to transforming the existing products into unique products and offering a unique product. According to Robbins and Judge (2013), creativity means combining ideas in unique ways or create continuity between the ideas. Creativity, therefore, is considered a key input for recognizing business ideas (Smith et al., 2016). Creativity is seen as a behavior that generates useful ideas for the development of the organization, and leaders play a vital role in promoting creativity by promoting openness and applying non-traditional and imaginative thinking while solving the problem (Ellen Mathisen et al., 2012).

Organizations will never be able to continue their lives without creativity and innovation (Holagh et al., 2014; Durrah et al., 2017). To have a creative and innovative idea, it is necessary to have the following three attributes: (Subjectivity, Novelty, and Effectivity). Shahhosseinia and Taghizadeh (2016) noted that knowledge and information are the basis for creativity. The culture of creativity depends on many factors such as structural characteristics and management practices (Yılmaz, 2010). The difference in personality traits can affect creativity styles (Ee et al., 2007).

The general atmosphere leads to cooperation and creativity, and it is a proven fact that the perception of the relationship between the person and the environment and creativity is conditioned by the personality traits and the different perceptions of the surrounding world (Durrah, et al., 2015; Sokol et al., 2015).

Conflict Management and Creativity

For true innovation and good ideas, human conflict, argument, and debate are needed (Heffernan, 2015). Adamas (2006) also noted that encouraging diversity among team members is essential. Thus, the key to creativity lies in encouraging interaction and conflict among employees. Successful organizations require their employees to think creatively and to integrate conflicting demands (Miron-Spektor et al., 2011). Conflicts generate creative decisions, but the conflict, argument, and debate of tasks are detrimental to their implementation because of disagreements and a reduced willingness to work together in the future as a group (Jehn and Bendersky, 2003). Task conflict can be useful for creativity because it increases the tendency of group members and scrutinizes their task issues (Bai et al., 2016). So, the conflict has to be stimulated, as it has a positive influence on the innovation and creativity of employees.

There are a number of outcomes of resolving the conflict in an appropriate and effective manner such as maximum efficiency, talent, and creativity (Shahhosseini and Taghizadeh, 2016). Creativity helps problem-solving, yet our understanding of it is still forming. In addition, it seems problem formulation and problem-solving concern different domains of creativity (Schmidt, 2016).

Working environments with conflict at undesirable levels are less likely to maintain creativity (Morris, 2004). The optimal level of conflict can stimulate creativity when resolving and handling issues. Therefore, conflict is considered positive in organizational environments (Omisore and Abiodun, 2014).

Thus, some conflict is important to make the relationship more reliable and interesting, and even conflict is essential to group innovation and creativity (Johnsen and Lacoste, 2016). Hence, conflict can be constructive in work settings. However, conflict at an undesired level can be harmful for the organization (Omisore and Abiodun, 2014). In other words, the relationship between conflict in the organization and creativity takes a positive direction to a certain extent and then can turn into a negative trend. Thus, from the above-mentioned literature, this study is trying to examine the following Hypotheses:

H₁: Collaboration style has a positive impact on creativity.

H₂: Avoidance style has a positive impact on creativity.

H₃: Accommodation style has a positive impact on creativity.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Measures

This study contains two main variables; the conflict management styles represent the independent variables of this research. The scale has been adopted based on Rahim Organizational conflict inventory II ROCI-II (Rahim, 1983; Rahim and Magner, 1995) measured by 19 items (Collaboration (7 items), Avoidance (6 items), and Accommodation (6 items)). The dependent variable of this research was the creativity, and its 13-item scale has been adapted from Zhou and George (2001). A Likert scale has been adopted that includes five grades from strongly disagree to agree strongly.

Research Sample

The research was applied on two petrochemical companies, namely: 1) The Oman Liquefied Natural Gas LLC (Oman LNG) and 2) The Oman India Fertiliser Company (OMIFCO) located in the South East Governorate of Oman. Using a questionnaire, data were collected via random sample method from employees in administrative, technical, and production departments. (147) out of (200) questionnaires distributed (87%) were suitable for statistical analysis (99 from Oman LNG and 48 from OMIFCO)

The sample comprised (72.79%) males and (27.21%) females, due to the industrial nature of the company. The participants' age percentage was (61.22%) for ages less than 35, (34.02%) ranged from 35 to less than 45 years and (4.76%) aged 45 and older. As for the education of the participants, high secondary school or less (9.53%), diploma (38.77%), bachelor degree (42.17%), higher Studies (9.53%). Regarding years of experience, (21.1%) have service less than 5 years, (40.13%) for 5 to less than 10 years and (38.77%) for 10 years of service and more. As to functional position, (30.61%) of administrators, (8.16%) financier, (6.12%) marketers, (36.74%) technicians, and (18.37%) from other departments.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Reliability

Cronbach's alpha used to measure reliability. Table 1 displays the results of reliability analysis for conflict management styles and creativity. The coefficient values of all research variables were above (0.7) indicating that all variables are reliable.

Table 1: Reliability Coefficient Analysis

	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of items
Collaboration	.822	7
Avoidance	.919	6
Accommodation	.748	6
Creativity	.876	13

Validity

Both Content and Face validities were examined in this study. During the development stage of a questionnaire, Crano and Brewer (2014) emphasized that a safe and sound means to assure content validity is through consulting a panel of expert. Thus, in the current study, content validity was evaluated by consulting five professors specialized in HRM and management at Dhofar University.

After the measure has been developed, Face validity was also determined (Nunnally and Bernstein, 2010). A group of 16 people working in the two companies was requested to review and evaluate the questionnaire. According to their recommendations, changes were implied in the measurement instrument.

Mean and standard deviation of variables

Table 2 illustrates the descriptive statistics (arithmetic mean, standard deviation) of job conflict management styles and creativity. The comparison among conflict management styles displays that the most effective style used by employees to manage conflict is the Collaboration, followed by the Accommodation and lastly Avoidance.

Table 2 shows that the collaboration style has a very high value and play the main role in managing conflict, and shows that it is essential for employees to integrate the wants of conflicted ones into a suitable solution maximizing the benefits for both parties. In addition, the mean value of accommodation style, as shown in Table 3, is high. This implies that employees are usually sacrificing their own aims to satisfy the needs of others. However, the conflict style has a medium-level value that is slightly higher than the hypothetical mean (3) and indicates that employees will sometimes allow conflicts to go unresolved. This information can be considered useful for managers when solving employees' conflict matters. Moreover, table 3 shows that the level of creativity in the organization is high.

Table 2: Means and Std. Deviations of Conflict Management Styles and Creativity

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Collaboration	4.3033	.47392
Avoidance	3.1971	.91371
Accommodation	3.8074	.57181
Creativity	4.1222	.45829

n = 147

Correlations among Variables

Table 3 shows the correlation coefficients among the research variables. As it is clear from this table, different styles of conflict management had a different relationship with creativity. The result shows that there is a moderate and positive correlation (.524) between collaboration and creativity. This relationship was highly significant ($p=0.000$). This result reveals that the higher the collaboration style level, the stronger will be the creativity. However, the correlation coefficient for avoidance and creativity was a negligible positive correlation (.166), and it was significant (.045). Finally, the result for accommodation style and creativity was highly

significant ($p=0.000$) with low positive correlation (.428). This result indicates that employees who practice the accommodation style, have a higher possibility for creativity in an organization.

Moreover, the results show that there is no significant correlation between collaboration and avoidance styles that imply that those employees who practice the collaboration style are less likely to follow the avoidance style. However, there was a positive correlation (.406) with high significance (.000) between avoidance and accommodation styles and imply those employees who practice avoidance my practice accommodation style, too.

Table 3: Correlation Coefficients

	1	2	3	4
1. Collaboration	1			
2. Avoidance	.149	1		
3. Accommodation	.406**	.456**	1	
4. Creativity	.524**	.166*	.428**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level;

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Multiple Regression Analysis

To test the hypothesis, multiple regression analysis was used as depicted in Table 4. Both collaboration and accommodation styles appear to have an effect on creativity with a significant value of $\beta = 0.419$ and 0.265 ($p = .000$ and $.002$), respectively. These results show that both H1 and H3 are not rejected, while the result showed that avoidance style has no influence on creativity $\beta = -.017$ ($p = .823$), so H2 was rejected.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analyses

Independent Variables	β	T	R	R ²	F
Collaboration	.419***	5.568***			
Avoidance	-.017	-.224			
Accommodation	.265**	3.174			
			.575	.330	23.325***

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, $n=147$

V. Discussion and Implications

As stated earlier, the aim of the current research is to examine the effect of conflict management styles on creativity. Both collaboration and accommodation styles were found to have a significant and positive impact on creativity; whereas the results revealed that avoidance style had no influence on creativity. This positive influence of collaboration style on creativity reveals the strong relationship between the two variables and also reflects to the features added by collaboration to the creativity values such as problem-solving, changeability, and the spirit of taking risks and this evidence provide managers an idea on how to trigger creativity by focusing on collaboration style of conflict management. On the other hand, the results show that avoidance style has no effect on creativity in the petrochemical industry, and these results reveal that there is no role of avoidance style to affect creativity, and these results require the HR managers to give training for their employees to avoid practicing avoidance style while managing conflict. Also, the study indicated that the accommodation style has a

significant effect on creativity. There was a scarce in the literature regarding the studies that address the direct effect of conflict styles and creativity.

VI. Practical Implications

Based upon the above mentioned, it can be argued that the conflict management collaboration and accommodation styles influence creativity positively. Therefore, Petrochemical Companies in Oman should pay more attention to styles of conflict management practices by employees to build creativity and which in turn leads to better solve problem abilities, changeability, and spirit of innovative working. In addition, HR managers need to support the collaboration style by enhancing trust among employees. Trust provides employees the confidence to be open and encourage them to exchange of information to reach to the optimal solutions (Bacon and Blyton, 2007). However, employees will be reluctant to share problems and areas of mutual concern knowing that the information will be used against them (Zaheer and Zaheer, 2006). Moreover, managers need to develop and implement cooperative problem-solving processes by spreading the spirit of open-minded discussion of conflicting perspectives through listening and understanding each other's opinion and concerns. These recommendations are not easy to implement in a short span of time; however, when done, they can boost business creativity successfully and effectively.

VII. Limitation and Future Research

This study provides help policymakers of companies to employ a suitable style of conflict management as it is found to be one of the main drivers of creativity in an organization. On the other hand, this study has several limitations: the results cannot be generalized, due to small sample size, also, the study focused on the petrochemical industry. So, future researchers can examine other industries with larger sample size.

VIII. Conclusions

This study has investigated the effect of three styles of conflict management on creativity in the Omani context with reference to the petrochemical sector. The findings offer an understanding of employee behavior in the petrochemical organizations in Oman and thus provided managers an insight to understand how to use different styles of conflict management in enhancing the creativity of employees. So, the current study confirms that the concepts of conflict management are without a doubt are essential and critical factors for the petrochemical companies in particular and for other sectors in general.

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